

Studies on some Monofluophosphates : Part V.

E. B. Singh and P. C. Sinha

The dissociation pressures at different temperatures of the monofluophosphates of cadmium, manganese, nickel, and chromium have been measured. In case of nickel and chromium breaks have been noticed in the $p-t$ curves indicating the existence of different modifications of the salts. The values of the dissociation pressure have been used to compare the stability of the compound. From the plot of $\log p$ against $1/T$ heat of dissociation per gm. molecule has been found out in each case. The change in free energy ΔF and entropy ΔS have been calculated. The positive values of ΔS obtained supports that the dehydration is spontaneous.

A salt hydrate being heated dissociates into a lower hydrate or anhydrous salt, and water vapour. The system becomes univariant and to each temperature there corresponds a certain definite vapour pressure which is independent of the amount of the phases. By applying the Van't Hoff equation the heat of hydration per gm.mol can be calculated

$$\frac{d \log p}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2}$$

$$-\Delta H = \frac{\log p_1 - \log p_2}{1/T_1 - 1/T_2} \times R \times 2.303$$

where ΔH = heat of hydration per gm.mol.

p_1 and p_2 are the vapour pressures at abs.temp. T_1 and T_2 .

Free energy and Entropy changes are calculated with the help of the equation

$$\Delta F = RT \log_e p_2/p_1$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta F}{T}$$

where p_2 is the dissociation pressure of the hydrate and p_1 the vapour pressure of water at temp. T .

In the present work dissociation pressures of the hydrates of cadmium, manganese, nickel, and chromium monofluophosphates¹ were determined by static method at varying temperatures. The heat of dissociation was calculated from the slope of the linear graph $\log p$ against $1/T$. The values of ΔF and ΔS were also calculated.

The apparatus employed for measuring the dissociation pressure is the same as used by Sinha and Ray² with some improvement and modification. A series of measurements were made at approximately 5° intervals in ascending order of temperature. The pressure at lower temperature was found too small to be measured advantageously, and at higher temperature the rate of hydrolysis was found to be appreciable.

1. E. B. Singh and P. C. Sinha, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 407.
2. P. C. Sinha and R. C. Ray, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 790.

DISCUSSION

$CdPO_3F \cdot 8/3 H_2O/H_2O$: From the pressure composition curve³ (isothermal) it has been noticed that only two hydrates of cadmium monofluophosphates $CdPO_3F \cdot 8/3 H_2O$ and $CdPO_3F \cdot H_2O$ are stable. As the pressure exerted by monohydrate is very low only the dissociation pressure of $CdPO_3F \cdot 8/3 H_2O$ has been measured.

The dissociation pressure rises continuously as the temperature is raised. The plot of $\log p$ against $1/T$ is almost a straight line and the decomposition has been found reversible. Beyond 70° suddenly the value of the pressure rises sharply and becomes nearly the same as that of water vapour, and the hydrate has been found to be irreversibly decomposed.

$MnPO_3F \cdot 2H_2O/H_2O$: Being efflorescent $MnPO_3F \cdot 4H_2O$ is not stable at room temperature (about 30°). From pressure composition isothermal study³ it appears that only two hydrates $MnPO_3F \cdot 2H_2O$ and $MnPO_3F \cdot H_2O$ are stable at 50° . The pressure exerted by mono hydrate is very low and has not been measured.

The dissociation pressure rises continuously and the plot of $\log p$ against $1/T$ is straight line.

$NiPO_3F \cdot 7H_2O/6H_2O$: It was found³ that out of two stable hydrates $NiPO_3F \cdot 7H_2O$ and $NiPO_3F \cdot 6H_2O$ the latter exerts a very low pressure. Therefore the dissociation pressure of only $NiPO_3F \cdot 7H_2O$ has been measured.

The dissociation pressure rises continuously as the temperature is raised. At above 55° there is a slight break in the $p-t$ curve which is more evident from the plot of $\log p$ against $1/T$. The break gives evidence of a transition point at that temperature. The compound obtained by heating the original substance at about 50° and above 60° corresponds to same molecular formula $NiPO_3F \cdot 6H_2O$, but there is difference in colour, the former is bluish green and the latter green. This suggests that there may be two modifications of hexa hydrate having same molecular formula.

$Cr_2(PO_3F)_3 \cdot 18 H_2O/15 H_2O$: The pressure composition isothermal study³ indicated the existence of $Cr_2(PO_3F)_3 \cdot 18H_2O$, $Cr_2(PO_3F)_3 \cdot 15H_2O$, and $Cr_2(PO_3F)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ as definite hydrates stable at the condition of the experiment. As there are unstable lower hydrates next to $Cr_2(PO_3F)_3 \cdot 15H_2O$ which is evident from the zeolytic nature of the pressure composition curve, the pressure temperature study was not found advantageous of the lower hydrates.

In this case also at 51.5° the direction of the curve changes and a break has been observed at that temperature suggesting the existence of two dissociating compounds, one stable below 51.5° and the other above it. The colour of the substance becomes more green.

From the plot of $\log p$ against $1/T$ heat of dissociation per gm. mol. has been calculated. The values of ΔF and ΔS have been also found out. The value of ΔS , as expected for the reaction in which the number of species increases, is positive.

TABLE

System	t°C	ΔH cal/mole	ΔF cal/mole	ΔS e.u.
CdPO ₃ F 8/3H ₂ O/H ₂ O	50.25	8000	1094	21.3
MnPO ₃ F 2H ₂ O/H ₂ O	50.0	8270	1316	21.5
NiPO ₃ F 7H ₂ O/6H ₂ O	29.8	11200	26.96	36.8
„	60.5	9350	35.208	27.9
Cr ₂ (PO ₃ F) ₃ 18H ₂ O/15H ₂ O	50.0	16000	151.9	49.06
„	59.7	10000	134.3	29.06

Department of Chemistry,
Magadh University,
Gaya (Bihar).

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